

THIOKETONIC ESTERS. PART VII. THIO-THIOL ESTIMATION.

By S. K. MITRA.

A method for the estimation of the thio-thiol has been described. Substitution at the α -carbon atom of β -thio-ketonic esters increases the percentage of thiol. The factors governing this equilibrium have been clearly established. The existence of a third phase—an enol, isomer of these esters has been suggested.

The orthodox bromination method for keto-enol estimation (Meyer, *Annalen*, 1911, 380, 212) could not be suitably used in the case of β -thio-ketonic esters due to following reasons:

1. Various reactions were likely to occur, over and above the addition of bromine at the double bond, *e.g.* (a) oxidation of thiol to disulphide; (b) further oxidation to sulphone; (c) addition of bromine to the sulphide.

2. Part of bromine might react with the reactive hydrogen atom of the methylene group.

3. Addition to the double bond might not be quantitative.

It was thought that alcoholic iodide could be suitably used in determining thiol in such compounds.

The process underlying this method invokes the property of iodine to oxidise a thiol (I) to a disulphide (II).

The result of the experiments have been described in Table I. A rise of temperature depresses thiolisation, which is in conformity with the effect on oxygen analogue (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE I.

Esters.	The percentage of thiol in EtOH at		
	30°.	40°.	60°.
Me·CS·CH ₂ ·CO ₂ Et	41·0	—	38·7
Me·CS·CHMe·CO ₂ Et	62·8	61·9	60·0
Me·CS·CH·CO ₂ Et	—	—	64·4
$\begin{array}{c} \\ \text{CH}_2\text{·CH·Me}_2 \\ \text{Me·CS·CH·(CO}_2\text{Et)}_2 \end{array}$	61·1	—	58·5

At ordinary temperature, ethyl thioacetoacetate contains nearly six times as much thiol as the enol in ethyl acetoacetate under similar conditions. Ethyl methylthioacetoacetate on the other hand contains a higher percentage of thiol than ethyl thioacetoacetate and this is the opposite to what was expected from the relation of ethyl methylacetoacetate and ethyl acetoacetate (*loc. cit.*) though in each case rise of temperature favours thioketomisation. It is also evident that substitution in ethyl thioacetoacetate increases the percentage of thiol. The order is represented as

The paradox that an increase of thiol due to the introduction of an electron pushing group clearly points out the existence of some condition other than the activation of the methylene group in the immediate neighbourhood of thiocarbonyl group, which controls the equilibrium.

There are certain activating groups (Lapworth, *Lit. Phil. Soc. Manchester*, 1920, 64, iii, 1) which by virtue of their tendency to repel or attract electrons from a system acting in the form of electron source in the former and electron sink in the latter (Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1305) create an increased tendency for an atom or a group in the system to separate as a positive or a negative ion, to combine with other external polarised molecules in a reaction. In the case of the thioketonic esters both C=S and -COOEt act as an electron sink and thus increase the tendency of the hydrogen atom of the methylene group to part as a positive ion. An altogether different behaviour *viz.*, mobility of this hydrogen atom to that of methane is evidently due to this incipient ionised condition, which used to be known as active state. Such activation is necessary to endow the hydrogen atom with a tendency to react with an unsaturated system either intermolecularly—aldol condensation, Michael's and Thorpe's reactions—or intramolecularly—triad and keto-enol tautomerism. Keto-enol tautomerism is, evidently a manifestation of an internal additive process—direct and retrograde, if it is, as suggested by Ingold (*Chem. Ind.*, 1923, 42, 1246), considered to be an internal aldol condensation. The duty of the activating group is finished by imparting the required mobility to the hydrogen atom; it is the unsaturation of the groups in tautomerides—C=O, C=C, in β ketonic esters and β diketones; C=S, C=C in corresponding sulphur analogues which control the distribution. Hence the tendency of saturation of these groups is the main factor governing the equilibrium. It is not difficult to imagine a case where

two unsaturated groups, *e.g.*, C=O and C=S with C=C, are competing for a hydrogen atom—the greater the unsaturation, the greater the share of hydrogen—a phenomenon though not identical but comparable with the distribution of a base between two acids. The greater percentage of thiol in ethyl thioacetoacetate than enol in the oxygen analogue is evidently due to the greater unsaturated character of the thiocarbonyl group. The increased thiolisation resulting from the substitution at the α -carbon atom in ethyl thioacetoacetate is due to the weakening of the unsaturated character of the C=C group in the substituted system. For a similar reason the carbonyl group of aldehydes is more reactive than that of ketones.

The almost equal percentage of enol in ethyl acetoacetate and its methyl derivative as determined by Meyer's method (if the method be taken for granted as correct) can be accounted for if β -ketonic esters be assumed to exist in three phases—A, B and C—at any time.

Meyer's method of bromination gives an estimation of the sum total of the phases (A) and (B). The introduction of a methyl group at the α -carbon atom evidently depresses the phase (B) by an amount almost equal to the increase of phase (A). The possibility of the existence of phase (B) was first suggested by Lapworth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 30). According to him, initial enolisation is necessary for a ketone or an ester to react with bromine giving rise to α -bromo derivatives. The view has been confirmed by Ward (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2212) who isolated intermediate compounds in some cases. Burton and Dawson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1289) have been able to confirm that substitution is preceded by isomeric transformation of an aldehyde from the ketonic to the enolic form. Meyer (*Ber.*, 1922, 45, 2864) has also pointed out that enolisation of malonic acid is necessary before actual bromination takes place. This view has been confirmed by West (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1277). According to the hypothesis of electronic displacement, any carboxylic compound (III) has a tendency to pass on to (IV).

Augmentation or retardation depends upon the nature of group 'X', where X is hydroxyl, as in the case of acetic acid; there will be a little tendency for a proton to become loosened from the methyl group, since the carboxyl group is self-contained (Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1618). No such adjustment of co-valencies of the carbonyl carbon is possible when 'X' is halogen, alkyl or hydrogen and hence loosening of a proton in these cases will occur with greater facility. The loosened proton is attracted towards negative carbonyl oxygen and enolisation takes place. In the case of β -ketoic esters, inspite of the impeding nature of 'X' = OEt, the optimum conditions necessary for the phase (C) to pass on to (B) are supplied by the ketoic group already present. The greater percentage of enol in β -diketones is evidently due to the absence of any retarding group like OEt. In the case of symmetrical systems, e.g., acetylacetone, dibenzoylmethane, triacetylmethane, the number of enol isomerides (e.g. phases A and B) remains fixed. But in the case of unsymmetrical systems e.g., benzoylacetone, β -ketoic esters, the number of enol isomerides increases with the increase of carbonyl groups. The result of Meyer's method of bromination is the algebraic sum of the percentages of all the enol isomerides present in the tautomeric compounds. Hence, the bromination method is quite helpless in the estimation of any particular enol isomer. The iodometric method is capable of giving an exact measurement of one of the isomers (V) of thioketoic esters. The estimation of isomer (VI) could not be effected since no reagent could be available at present which would estimate it leaving the isomer (V) unaffected. The work is, however, in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Thioketoic esters required in this investigation were prepared according to the method described by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 18, 3).

In the case of ordinary mercaptans it was found that even at as low a temperature as -7° , iodine solution could be decolourised as rapidly as at ordinary temperature with a sharp end-point. The incapability of ethyl crotonate to absorb any iodine indicated that the double bond present in enolised β -thioketonic esters could not share any iodine used for thiol estimation. On the other hand, the absence of any halogen in the resulting compound after titration confirmed that under the conditions of the experiment the thiocarbonyl group did not absorb iodine to form an additive compound. Error due to displacement of equilibrium in the course of titration was also found to be negligible since a quantity of the ester after treatment with iodine until the colour just persisted, on being kept at the room temperature (15°) for five minutes, required only a few drops of a dilute solution of iodine to bring the colour back. Considering the slowness of the rate of thiolisation it was thought desirable to add an excess of iodine to the solution of the ester and to titrate the residual iodine with dilute thiosulphate. The results from both the methods agreed well. The estimations were performed in all cases under identical conditions as far as possible.

A known quantity of the ester was taken in 10 c. c. of a solvent (ethyl alcohol) in a hard glass test-tube and kept at the required temperature for six hours. A titration flask containing alcoholic iodine (50 c.c.) of known strength and some ethyl alcohol in a separate flask, were cooled to -7° . The ester from the thermostat was quickly added to the cooled alcoholic iodine solution, and the remaining contents of the tube were washed in with cooled alcohol (10 c.c. at -7°). The mixture was allowed to stand for about 25 seconds and the excess of iodine was titrated against a standard thiosulphate solution. In an experiment with a mercaptan, it was found that iodine did not take more than 5 seconds to oxidise the thiol. All the thio-esters required in this investigation were kept at room temperature (15°) for 4 weeks before the thiol was estimated.

TABLE II.

Me. CS·CH₂·CO₂Et.

Ester.	Temp.	Iodine. (0.06722N)	Thiosulphate. (0.03126N)	Thiol.
0.4904 g.	30°	25 c.c. diluted with 25 c.c. EtOH	9.6 c.c.	41.08%
0.4900	60°	Do	12.2	38.7

TABLE II (contd.).

Me·CS·CH·(Me)CO₂Et.

Ester.	Temp.	0·0505N-Iodine.	0·03239N-Thiosulphate	Thiol.
0·5276 g.	30°	50 c.c.	14·0 c.c.	62·87%
0·5517	40°	„	12·0	61·97
0·5432	60°	„	15·1	60·01

Me·CS·CH·(CH₂CH : Me₂)CO₂Et.

Ester.	Temp.	0·0672N-Iodine.	0·03126N-Thiosulphate.	Thiol.
0·3750 g.	60°	30 c.c.	15·5 c.c.	64·42%

Me·CS·CH·CO₂Et

Ester.	Temp.	0·06719N-Iodine.	0·02754N-Thiosulphate	Thiol.
0·5672 g.	30°	25 c.c., diluted with 25 c.c. of EtOH	3·2 c.c.	61·16%
0·5723	60°	Do	5·2	58·53

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KING'S COLLEGE,
LONDON.

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